

Data Collection Matrix Plugins de SEO

PLUGINS WITH STRUCTURED DATA DETECTED	JSON-LD	MICRODATA	SCHEMA.ORG - MAIN BLOCKS													SCHEMA.ORG - SECONDARY BLOCKS							
	Schema.org	Data-vocabulary.org	WEBPAGE	WEBSITE	ORGANIZATION	CORPORATION	PROFESSIONAL SERVICE	ARTICLE	WHEADER	WPFOOTER	BREADCRUMBLIST	SITE NAVIGATION ELEMENT	PERSON	BLOGPOSTING	LOCAL BUSINESS	Webpage	WebSite	Organization	ContactPoint	PostalAddress	Person	Article	GeoCoordinates
Plugin01	x		x														x	x					
Plugin02	x		x														x	x	x				
Plugin03	x			x			x													x			x
Plugin04	x			x	x																		
Plugin06	x				x														x				
Plugin07	x		x																x				
Plugin11	x		x														x	x					
Plugin13	x				x														x				
Plugin15	x			x				x										x					
Plugin17	x		x	x			x											x	x		x	x	
Plugin25	x			x				x											x	x			x
Plugin28	x				x															x			
Plugin35	x				x														x				
Plugin46	x			x	x				x	x	x								x				
Plugin53	x			x	x			x				x	x	x		x				x			x
Plugin54	x			x	x								x										
Plugin59	x				x														x	x			
Plugin63	x			x	x								x										
Plugin67	x														x					x			x
Plugin82		x																					
TOTAL (20)	19	1	5	9	11	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	4	8	6	1	1	4